

SELF SENSING GLASS/EPOXY CROSS-PLY LAMINATES FOR DAMAGE MONITORING: AN ANALYTICAL MODEL

M. Zappalorto, P.A. Carraro, F. Panozzo, M. Quaresimin

Department of Management and Engineering, University of Padova
Stradella San Nicola 3, 36100, Vicenza, Italy
Email: michele.zappalorto@unipd.it, web page: <http://www.gest.unipd.it/it>

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ABSTRACT

Damage monitoring during the in-service life is very important for the safe use of composite materials in advanced applications. In this view self sensing materials, obtained by nano-modification of the polymer matrix, have a strong potential in detecting damage initiation and evolution. In the present work a closed form solution is presented to accurately predict the variation of the electrical resistance in conductive (CNTs doped) crossply laminates, caused by matrix cracking in the transverse layers. The accuracy of the proposed model is verified by comparison to a bulk of FE analyses.

1 INTRODUCTION

The static and fatigue behaviour of multidirectional laminates made of unidirectional (UD) plies is characterised by the initiation and propagation of cracks in the off-axis plies, with a continuous increasing of the crack density with the static load level [1-3] or the number of cycles [4-7] and resulting in the degradation of the composite elastic properties.

Accordingly, health monitoring for the detection of the damage is essential to improve the in service reliability and lifetime of FRP-structures. This is the reason why many types of sensors for damage sensing have been developed in the last years.

Very recently the interest of the scientific community has moved to self sensing capability of composite parts, obtained measuring the electrical conductivity of the FRP material with carbon nanotubes (CNT)- or carbon black (CB)-doped polymer matrices.

Indeed, adding limited amounts of CNTs or CB in the matrix of advanced fibre FRP can lead to electrically conductive composites, as widely reported in the literature [8-14].

Boger and co-authors [15] reported results on incremental quasi static tests on [0/45/90/-45/45/90/-45/0] glass/CB-doped epoxy laminates showing that it was possible to correlate the irreversible electrical resistance increase, measured in DC current during the tests, with the residual strain resulting from damage onset and growth in the laminates. However, the authors did not report observations of the damage mechanisms and their relationship with the change in the electrical properties. Similar conclusions were drawn by Fernberg and Joffe [16].

Gao and co-authors [17] carried out static tests on glass/CNT-modified epoxy cross-ply laminates with lay-up [0/90n/0] and showed that damage was characterised by an evolution of the density of transverse cracks as the strain increased, followed by the onset and propagation of delaminations. It was shown that the increase in the crack density corresponded to an irreversible increase in the electrical resistance of the cross-ply laminates along the loading direction. Then, the onset and propagation of delaminations caused a further and steeper resistance increase.

Abry et al. [18] carried out static tests on cross-ply laminates made of carbon fibres and epoxy resin, without the use of CNTs or CB, exploiting the conductivity of carbon fibres for electrical measurements and found that the electrical resistance measured applying an AC current increased with the applied strain. However they did not report correlations between these increments and the crack density. They also observed that, concerning carbon fibre composites, AC measurements were capable of detecting the onset and evolution of transverse cracks, while DC measurements highlighted the evolution of fibre-related damage [18].

Similar results were obtained by Todoroki et al. [19] who found that an AC electrical resistance increase could be associated to the transverse crack density evolution in cross-ply laminates made of carbon fibres and epoxy resin.

After this brief review, it is clear that the chance of detecting damage onset and evolution in terms of off-axis cracks formation in composite laminates by means of self-sensing systems is very attractive and promising. However, at present, modelling efforts aimed at providing analytical tools for correlating the resistance increase to the state of damage in multidirectional laminates (crack density and/or stiffness degradation) are very limited.

Finite Element (FE) analyses were carried out by Todoroki and co-authors [20] to study the effect of transverse cracks and delaminations in the electrical resistance of cross-ply laminates with surface probes as those tested and presented in Ref. [19].

Ogi [21] proposed an analytical model for the piezoresistance behaviour of cross-ply laminates in the presence of transverse cracks. To this aim the crack was considered as a circuitual element whose resistance depends on the crack density according to polynomial functions which require the calibration of several parameters by means of experimental data fitting.

In this scenario, a fully analytical model to correlate the electrical resistance increase to the crack density of a multidirectional laminate would be highly desirable.

As a first step towards this goal, in the present work an analytical model is first presented to predict the DC electrical resistance change of cross-ply laminates as a function of the density of transverse cracks. The validity of the proposed model is verified by comparison to a bulk of FE analyses showing a very satisfactory agreement.

2 A MODEL TO ASSESS THE ELECTRICAL RESISTANCE CHANGE DUE TO TRANSVERSE CRACKING

Consider the cross-ply laminate with regularly spaced cracks in the transverse layer shown in figure 1). Under these conditions the crack density ρ equates the inverse of the inter-distance between cracks, denoted here as l . this assumption allows to simplify the analysis by considering a laminate segment between two cracks regarded as representative of the overall laminate behaviour (see fig. 2). with reference to the coordinate system shown in figure 1, suppose the laminate is provided with a potential difference along the x direction, ΔV_x , so that an electrical resistance change occurs when transverse cracks initiate and it continuously increases while the crack density increases [15].

Within this scenario, the ratio of the global resistance in the presence of damage to its initial value (undamaged state), R_x/R_{x0} , is the same for the entire laminate and for the representative segment between two cracks, which is subjected to the specific potential difference $\Delta V_{x,s} = \Delta V_x / (L \rho)$.

With reference to the geometry shown in figure 2, the following analytical expression has been proposed in Ref. [22] to link the electrical resistance change to the crack density within the cross-ply laminate:

$$\frac{R_x}{R_{x0}} = 1 + (1 - \varphi) \frac{2\rho}{\alpha} \frac{\eta_x^0}{\eta_x^{90}} \cdot \frac{h_{90}}{h_0} \operatorname{Tanh} \frac{\alpha}{2\rho} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Cross-ply laminate with transverse cracks subjected to a potential difference ΔV_x

Figure 2: Representative laminate segment between two transverse cracks

Where [22]:

- h_{90} and h_0 are the thickness of the 90 and 0 layer, respectively;
- implicitly assuming an orthotropic behaviour, (η_x^0, η_x^{90}) are the electrical resistivity of the plies in the x directions;
- α is a parameter depending on the thickness of the plies, and on the electrical resistivity of the plies in the through-the-thickness direction
- φ is a parameter quantifying the crack closure phenomenon.

3 VALIDATION BY COMPARISON TO NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, the accuracy of the analytical framework developed in the previous section is checked versus a large bulk of FE analyses carried out using the commercial code ANSYS® 13.

Electrically conductive analyses were carried out, initially, using 8-nodes plane elements (PLANE 230 in Ansys).

A schematic of the FE model and boundary conditions in terms of electric potential V and current density j_x used in the analyses are shown in Figure 3, whereas a vector plot of the current density from the FE model is shown in figure 4.

Figure 3: Boundary conditions in the electrical FE model.

An element size of 0.05 mm was used, small enough to guarantee accurate results in terms of global resistance, evaluated as $R_x = l(V_1 - V_0)/I$, where I is the average current density in the half segment multiplied by the total thickness $h = h_0 + h_{90}$.

As a first example a Glass/CB-doped polyethylene with a single ply thickness of 0.3 mm was considered. Resistivity values, were taken from Markov et al. [9]. $[0/90_m]_s$ laminates were studied, with $m = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

FE results in terms of R_x/R_{x0} are plotted versus the crack density in Figure 5, where the satisfactory agreement between predictions based on Eq. (1) and numerical findings is evident, deviations being always lower than 3%.

Based on the results shown in Figure 6, it is noteworthy that, according to Eq. (1), the electrical resistance change increases while increasing, the crack density, as well as the 90° layer thickness.

The electrical resistance change depends on the η_x^{90}/η_x^0 ratio as documented in Figure 6, where a $[0/90_3]_s$ laminate is considered and R_x/R_{x0} is plotted against the crack density for different η_x^{90}/η_x^0 ratios. A sound agreement between FE results and analytical predictions can be noted, as well.

As a major conclusion to be drawn according to the results discussed in this section it can be stated that composite laminates manufactured with semi-conductive polymers are provided with remarkable self sensing capabilities, which also depend on parameters such as the thickness of the cracked layer and the ratio between the resistivity in the transverse and longitudinal direction. Moreover, it was proved that the analytical model developed in section 2 gives accurate predictions of the electrical resistance changes due to the presence of transverse cracks.

Figure 4: A vector plot of the current density from the FE model.

Figure 5: Electrical resistance ratio against crack density for cross-ply laminates. Resistivity values taken from [9]. Symbols: FE results, lines: model prediction.

Figure 6: Electrical resistance ratio against crack density for $[0/90_3]_s$ laminates; dots: FE results, lines: model prediction

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the present work, the results obtained from a closed form solution recently developed by the authors have been presented. Such a solution allows to accurately predict the variation of the electrical resistance change in conductive (CNTs doped) crossply laminates, caused by matrix cracking in the transverse layers. The accuracy of the proposed model is verified by comparison to a bulk of FE analyses, showing a very satisfactory agreement. It has been proven that the electrical resistance change increases while increasing the crack density, as well as the 90° layer thickness, and also depends on the η_x^{90}/η_x^0 ratio.

As a major conclusion it can be stated that composite laminates manufactured with semi-conductive polymers are provided with remarkable self sensing capabilities, which also depend on parameters such as the thickness of the cracked layer and the ratio between the resistivity in the transverse and longitudinal directions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. Varna, R. Joffe, N.V. Akshantala, R. Talreja, Damage in composite laminates with off-axis plies, *Composites Science and Technology*, **59**, 1999, pp. 2139-2147.
- [2] C.V. Singh, R. Talreja, A synergistic damage mechanics approach for composite laminates with matrix cracks in multiple orientations, *Mechanics of materials*, **41**, 2009, pp. 954-968.
- [3] C.V. Singh, R. Talreja, Evolution of ply cracks in multidirectional composite laminates, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, **47**, 2010, pp. 1338-1349.

- [4] J. Tong, Three Stages of Fatigue Crack Growth in GFRP Composite Laminates, *Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology*, **123**, 2001, pp. 139-143.
- [5] Z. Sun, I.M. Daniel, J.J. Luo, Modeling of fatigue damage in a polymer matrix composite, *Materials Science and Engineering*, **A361**, 2003, pp. 302-311.
- [6] K. Tohgo, S. Nakagawa, K. Kageyama, Fatigue behaviour of CFRP cross-ply laminates under on-axis and off-axis cyclic loading, *International Journal of Fatigue*, **28**, 2006, pp. 1254-1262.
- [7] M. Quaresimin, P.A. Carraro, L. Pilgaard Mikkelsen, N. Lucato, L. Vivian, P. Brøndsted, B.F. Sørensen, J. Varna, R. Talreja, Damage evolution under internal and external multiaxial cyclic stress state: a comparative analysis, *Composites: Part B: Engineering*, **61**, 2014, pp. 282–290.
- [8] F. H. Gojny, M. H.G. Wichmann, B. Fiedler, W. Bauhofer, K. Schulte, Influence of nano-modification on the mechanical and electrical properties of conventional fibre-reinforced composites, *Composites: Part A*, **36**, 2005, pp. 1525–1535.
- [9] A. Markov, B. Fiedler, K. Schulte, Electrical conductivity of carbon black/fibres filled glass-fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites, *Composites: Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp. 1390–1395.
- [10] M. H.G. Wichmann, J. Sumfleth, F. H. Gojny, M. Quaresimin, B. Fiedler, K. Schulte, Glass-fibre-reinforced composites with enhanced mechanical and electrical properties – Benefits and limitations of a nanoparticle modified matrix, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **73**, 2006, pp. 2346–2359.
- [11] E. T. Thostenson, T. W. Chou, Carbon nanotube networks: sensing of distributed strain and damage for life prediction and self healing, *Advanced Materials*, **18**, 2006, pp. 2837–2841.
- [12] T.W. Chou, L. Gao, E.T. Thostenson, Z. Zhang, J.-H. Byun, An assessment of the science and technology of carbon nanotube-based fibers and composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **70**, 2010, pp. 1-19.
- [13] N. Yamamoto, R. G. de Villoria, B. L. Wardle, Electrical and thermal property enhancement of fiber-reinforced polymer laminate composites through controlled implementation of multi-walled carbon nanotubes, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 2009–2015.
- [14] R. Samsur, V. K. Rangari, S. Jeelani, L. Zhang, Z. Y. Cheng, Fabrication of carbon nanotubes grown woven carbon fiber/epoxy composites and their electrical and mechanical properties, *Journal of Applied Physics*, **113**, 2013, pp. 214903
- [15] L. Boger, M. H.G. Wichmann, L. O. Meyer, K. Schulte, Load and health monitoring in glass fibre reinforced composites with an electrically conductive nanocomposite epoxy matrix, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 1886–1894.
- [16] S. P. Fernberg, R. Joffe, Damage detection in carbon fibre cross-ply laminates by aid of carbon nanotube doped resin, *In: Proceedings of the 13th European Conference on Composite Materials ECCM13*, June 2-5, 2008, Stockholm, Sweden
- [17] L. Gao, E. T. Thostenson, Z. Zhang, T. W. Chou, Sensing of Damage Mechanisms in Fiber-Reinforced Composites under Cyclic Loading using Carbon Nanotubes, *Advanced Functional Materials*, **19**, 2009, pp. 123–130.
- [18] J. C. Abry, Y. K. Choi, A. Chateauminois, B. Dalloz, G. Giraud, M. Salvia, In-situ monitoring of damage in CFRP laminates by means of AC and DC measurements, *Composites Science and Technology*, **61**, 2001, pp. 855-864.
- [19] A. Todoroki, K. Omagari, Y. Shimamura, H. Kobayashi, Matrix crack detection of CFRP using electrical resistance change with integrated surface probes, *Composites Science and Technology*, **66**, 2006, pp. 1539–1545.
- [20] A. Todoroki, M. Tanaka, Y. Shimamura, H. Kobayashi, Effects with a matrix crack on monitoring by electrical resistance method, *Advanced Composite Materials*, Vol. 13, No. 2, 2004, pp. 107–120.
- [21] K. Ogi, A Model for Piezoresistance Behavior in a CFRP Cross-Ply Laminate with Transverse Cracking, *Journal of Solid Mechanics and Materials Engineering*, Vol. 1, No. 8, 2007, pp. 975-985.

- [22] P.A. Carraro, M. Zappalorto, M. Quaresimin, An analytical model for the health monitoring of conductive cross-ply GF laminates via electric resistance measurements, Submitted for publication.